

An *ipso* aromatic substitution leading to a rare space group $P4_2\psi$

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Aromatic *ipso* substitution has led to 2,4,5-trimethoxy-1-nitrobenzene (**1**) belonging to the rare space group $P4_2\psi$. Thermolysis of (**1**) with sodium azide-DMSO gives a compound whose structure is being investigated.

An unexpected aromatic nitro substitution, in preference to halogen displacement was observed by one of us, during an "Attempted Synthesis of Dimethyl furoxanobenzofuroxan"¹. New highly sterically hindered nitrophenyl azides were prepared in large amounts², which were used successfully for microlithography and microelectronics with international patents being granted in most major countries of the west³. An *ipso* nitro di-decarboxylation, unexpectedly led to a new rapidly equilibrating benzofuroxan⁴, whose variable temperature NMR studies ("T-jump NMR") confirmed the simultaneous presence of two degenerate structures of this compound⁵. Only rapidly equilibrating benzofuroxans undergo the Beirut reaction, which has been used to prepare Indoloquinaxoline dioxide, marketed as 'Mecodex', by Pfizer Company as "a drug to combat dysentery and salmonellosis in swine". We have earlier prepared its new dimethoxy analogue. *Ips*o aromatic substitutions are well known in literature⁶. It has even been used in the synthesis of the antibiotic, Chuangxinmycin⁷, useful for controlling septicemia. *Ortho* substituents like the nitro, azo, acetyl, etc. are known to bring about tremendous rate acceleration in the cyclization of *o*-substituted nitrophenyl azides, the only exceptions being the nitrile and the methoxycarbonyl groups, which do not provide any rate acceleration⁸.

In our laboratory, thermolysis of azido-meta hemipinate led to a most unusual concomitant ring expansion and ring extrusion reaction yielding a new dimeric azepinylidinepyridyl acetate formed via a long lived singlet nitrene ("True nitrene"). The structure of the new

compound was established based on X-ray diffraction studies. The unusual structure was not anticipated from the spectral data^{9,10}.

Thermolysis and photolysis of nitroveratrole and dinitroveratrole, in the presence of alkali, has been studied by Sir Robert Robinson¹¹ and by Havinga and many Ph.D. thesis in the University of Leiden, have dealt with this topic¹².

'Thermal Cyclization of Aryl Semicarbazones', was attempted as a possible route to 1,2,3-benzotriazens. Spectral results surprised us in the first very step. In our hands, reaction of 4,5-dinitroveratrole, with methanolic-alkali, an unexpected aromatic nitro substitution gave 2,4,5-trimethoxy-1-nitrobenzene (**1**), instead of the expected nucleophilic substitution of a methoxyl group. This on reaction with alkali and chloroform, not unexpectedly, did not give any Reimer-Tiemann reaction. Spectral data pointed towards the unexpected results.

2,4,5-Trimethoxy-1-nitrobenzene (**1**)

The PMR and CMR spectra of the (**1**) are shown in Figs. 1 and 2 respectively.

A careful literature survey was again carried out at this stage. It was found that compound (**1**) had been prepared earlier by reaction of dinitroveratrole with alcoholic ammonia¹³ and with 1% KOH, followed by methylation¹⁴. It had also been prepared during the nitration of

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Fig. 1. PMR spectrum of (1).

Fig. 2. CMR spectrum of (1).

2,4,5-trimethoxy benzaldehyde where an *ipso* substitution of the aldehyde occurred¹⁵ and by nitration of 1,2,4-trimethoxybenzene (*loc. cit.*). It has also been prepared from Latifolin dimethyl ether using different acylium ions in the presence of Lewis acids to give 2,4,5-trimethoxynitrobenzene. Using Dihydrolatifolin dimethyl ether also gave the same nitro compound¹⁶. Nitrodecarboxylation and nitrodeformylation of some electron-rich benzoic acids and benzaldehydes¹⁷ has also been reported. The PMR and CMR data for 2,4,5-trimethoxy nitrobenzene from different authors are compared in Table 1.

X-Ray diffraction studies

Recent X-ray diffraction studies¹⁸ have shown that (1) is "achiral in solution, but crystallizes as a chiral structure in the tetragonal space group $P4_2$ with four symmetry-equivalent molecules in the unit cell. There is one molecule in the asymmetric unit". Only 30 compounds in the Cambridge Structural Database crystallize in space group $P4_2$, of which only two are non-organometallic compounds without chiral centers. 50% probability displacement ellipsoids and packing around the double helix around the 4_2 axis in the cell of the crystal (1) are shown in Figs. 3 and 4, respectively.

Table 1. Spectral data of (1)

	Observed values (300 MHz)	Literature values ¹⁸ (400 MHz)	Literature values ¹⁵ (500 MHz)
PMR (δ)	7.60 (1H, s, Ar-H)	7.58 (1H, s, H-6)	7.73 (1H, s, 6-H)
	6.56 (1H, s, Ar-H)	7.26 (1H, s, H-3)	6.70 (1H, s, 3-H)
	4.0 (6H, s, 4-OMe)	3.98 (3H, s, 4-OMe)	4.13 (3H, s, OMe)
	4.0 (6H, s, 5-OMe)	3.98 (3H, s, 5-OMe)	4.12 (3H, s, OMe)
	3.9 (3H, s, 2-OMe)	3.90 (3H, s, 2-OMe)	4.04 (3H, s, OMe)
CMR (ppm)	154.7 (C4)	154.85 (C4)	155.2 (C4)
	150.3 (C2)	150.36 (C2)	150.8 (C2)
	142.3 (C5)	142.56 (C5)	142.8 (C5)
	130.8 (C1)	131.15 (C1)	131.2 (C1)
	108.9 (C6)	109.20 (C6)	109.4 (C6)
	97.4 (C3)	97.96 (C3)	98.0 (C3)
	57.2 (OCH ₃)	57.32 (OCH ₃)	57.6 (OCH ₃)
	56.5 (OCH ₃)	56.61 (OCH ₃)	56.9 (OCH ₃)
	56.4 (OCH ₃)	56.48 (OCH ₃)	56.8 (OCH ₃)

Fig. 3. The molecular structure of (1), showing 50% probability displacement ellipsoids and the O5 and atom-numbering scheme (taken from Ref. 18).

Fig. 4. A view of the cell of (1), showing the methoxy double helix around the 4_2 axis and the contacts between atoms and other methoxy groups (taken from Ref. 18).

Compound (1) was then treated with NaN_3 and DMSO at 150°C and a yellowish orange product (2), m.p. 154°C was obtained. IR spectrum of (2) showed absorptions at 3429, 1749, 1625, 1594, 1533, 1507, 1372, 1290, 1233, 1090, 994 cm^{-1} . Mass, PMR and CMR spectra of (2) are shown below (Figs. 5–7) :

Its structure awaits confirmation by X-ray diffraction studies.

Fig. 5. MS of (2).

Fig. 6. CMR of (2).

Fig. 7. PMR of (2).

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